

CHALLENGES OF TRANSLATING DIPLOMATIC DISCOURSE AND TRANSLATION COMPETENCE

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Abstract: *This article aims to closely elaborate the comprehensive linguistic and stylistic features and aspects of equivalency regarding. The language of diplomacy and terminology has been extended particularly during the last three decades. The field of this style is closely related to activities concerned with meetings, conferences, congresses. It emphasizes that the whole range of these activities isn't devoid of proverbs and terminology which renders specific peculiarities.*

In the contrast to other fields the purpose of diplomatic texts, utterances and proverbs it's not that of merely conveying information but to serve the interests of a certain socio-political or ideological group. While others, I will primarily focus on analyzing the stylistic function of socio-political discourse and terminology owing to the fact that English is already being referred to as the language of contemporary diplomacy. Undoubtedly the growth linguistic predominance came as a result of political expansion. Also during the post-war world English was at a large perceived as cultural legacy of colonial era and technological revolution.

Nowadays English is at large extent being used in all spheres of diplomacy such as bilateral, multilateral agreements, public diplomacy.

Keywords: *proverbs, terminology, diplomatic discourse, stylistic function, linguistics, competence.*

Introduction

The latest historical improvements translation has been of English Language had a leading role and as a matter of fact, it has gained a global status at a large scale by being merely recognized in all corners of the world. As David Crystal emphasizes it is a language which is widely used in various mediums of communication in such domains as governments, law courts, media and educational system and to penetrate in different societies it is essential to master English Language. English language is being referred to as the language of diplomacy.

The main forum of political communication United Nation dates in 1945 and along with it there have been established numerous other international bodies such as World Bank (1945), UNESCO, UNICEF both in (1946), World Health Organization in (1948), and International Atomic Energy Agency (1957). The whole range of these bodies has been frequently represented in single meetings and the adoption of a single language to facilitate

communications in such contexts has been indispensable. Crystal (2003:29). Consequently, languages may be succinctly divided in dominant which is at a large extent subjugated to people and lingua franca which is freely accepted as a system of communication for mutual understanding. Snell-Hornby (1992:2006). This may succinctly explained by the fact that international politics broadly operates in various ways and incorporates several levels but presence of English is permanently evident. As a result, political protests, riots even peaceful lobbies next to embassies convey their messages in English.

In addition, it is worth emphasizing that translation has played a key role in international policy making and diplomacy (for example, the signing of bilateral and multilateral contracts, delivering speeches during state visits) and in national policy-making in particular for officially bilingual or multilingual countries. Schaffner. Contrary to other layers or lexical subdivisions, socio-political lexicon is comprised of distinctive features and reflects on social and ideological groupings, socio-economic relations, ideological matters etc. Due to the fact, the equivalence in meaning can't be considered a satisfactory criterion for an accurate translation as well as the idea that equivalence in meaning is merely provided by synonymy is ungrounded, lacking a sound argument.

Characteristics of translation competence

The simple features of translation competence, listed by Neubert (2000:5) are complexity, heterogeneity, approximation, open-endedness, creativity and historicity. Its complexity is best explained by the fact that translation is an intricate process entailing a variety of competences that are listed as intrinsic to translation competence.

All these skills do not necessarily need to be practised separately but may be

incorporated in practical translation classes. However, the skills are very different

from each other, which is another feature translation competence listed by Neubert (2000:5), namely heterogeneity. It specifies the skills required for translation as not only complex but also divergent as they comprise the knowledge possessed, technical abilities, cultural competence, linguistic skills and practical experience, all of them differing by nature and combined together as inherent parts.

The biggest array of these requirements explains another listed feature of translation competence, i.e. approximation. Translators “cannot be fully competent

unmanageable so they usually specialize in a limited number of core areas. Even

when it comes to the fields at which they are true experts, translators never cease to

search for new information or advice, which is another characteristic feature of

translation competence called open-endedness in the list. Translators never reach an absolute level of knowledge, however, they must never cease to make attempts.

One more feature is creativity or rather guided creativity as their constant

researching includes also an incessant quest for equivalence; the reason why it may

be called guided creativity is that they are always stimulated to search and create

new ways of saying something by a source text. The list ends with a feature called historicity which stresses the fact that, although at different points in history the approaches to translation were diverse and constantly changing, it may all be reduced to the need for flexibility common for translators throughout the ages.

Translation competence development requires taking all the characteristic

features of the competence into account. Complex and difficult though it may seem, the aim is to provide translation trainees with as rich and thorough translation education as possible. Thus, however challenging it appears to teach something that is described as open-ended and approximate, what is crucial in any approach is the recognition of the complexity or the open-endedness of the process of translation in any curricular model.

Translation Competence Development

In order to understand what the phenomenon involves, an attempt is made not only to define translation competence but also to specify how it develops and differentiate between its initial and terminal stage. The early manifestation of translation competence from which it derives is unquestionably linguistic competence. Taking into consideration the inevitability of a proficient command of language in the work of translators, this prerequisite may be assumed a necessary component of translation competence. It was Chomsky (1965: 4) who originated the term linguistic competence to describe a speaker's underlying ability to produce (and recognize) grammatically correct expressions. All bilinguals have at least some partial translational competence, if not innate then simply gained in the process of learning a language.

The fact is that each individual has diverse skills and thus also different mental structures of understanding. Bearing this universal truth in mind, Presas

declares that the development of translation competence consists basically of three

kinds of processes.

It emphasizes the need to approach each translation trainee individually and take his or her needs into consideration in the process of arranging and conducting the translation course they attend. Robinson elucidates that “we all learn in different ways, and institutional learning should therefore be as flexible and as complex and rich as possible, so as to activate the channels through which each student learns best” (2003: 49). Therefore, when translation educators, facing the multifarious challenge of translation competence development, additionally take more personal approach, the organization of translation class seems even more arduous. Bearing in mind that each translation task requires and employs a different set of skills, a combination of the universal competences crucial for novice translators must be decided on.

These two competences are therefore interdependent and inextricably linked

but in no way can they be assumed to be equivalent or to be the same. The PACTE

postulated that translation competence is qualitatively different from bilingual competence.

Conclusions:

- The professional translator has access to five different distinct kinds of knowledge TL(target language) knowledge, text type knowledge, SL (source language) knowledge, subject area (real-world) knowledge and contrastive language;

- Translation has been often defined with reference to meaning, and there it is frequently argued that the translation shall have the “same meaning” as the original;

- Translator is a communicator who bears the knowledge and skills which characterize a communicator;

- Generally, the term translation competence is process-oriented since

- it refers to the process of translation and skills used in this process, as opposed to

- the term translator competence which favours the product, i.e. the translator, at least from the perspective of translation education- together with the individual skills, background, education, experience, needs or progress (Pietrzak 2013). Kiraly (1995, 2000) who applied Socio Constructivist principles to translation education pioneered a student-centered approach which places responsibility on students and focuses on developing their competence through engaging in authentic translations, problem-based

and collaborative learning. Such a pedagogical approach favour the term translator competence to stress the importance of individual professional performance and shift the focus to the translator as well as the process-oriented research of translation.

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